

Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic Science and Technology Concepts among secondary school students in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State. Two research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental of non-randomized, pretest post-test control group design was adopted for the study. Two instruments; Self-Regulatory Behavior Inventory (SRBI) and Basic Science and Technology Performance Test ((BSTPT) were validated and used for data collection. Reliability coefficients of SRBI and BSTPT were established at 0.74 and 0.86 using Cronbach-Alpha Method and Kuder-Richardson-20 formula respectively. The sample size of 467 Middle basic II students during the 2023/2024 academic session was drawn from the population of 13,467 student using multi-stage sampling technique. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level using analysis of covariance, (ANCOVA). The result revealed a significant difference between the mean and self-regulatory behaviour and academic performance scores of students that were given homework after lesson and those who were not given homework. Based on these findings, it was concluded that homework strategy is effective in enhancing self-regulatory behaviour and academic performance of students in Basic Science and Technology. It was recommended among others that, homework strategy should be used during teaching and learning of BST particularly at lower, middle and upper basic levels of education.

Keywords: Homework, Performance, Self-Regulatory Behaviour, Basic Science and Technology concepts

Introduction

Education in science and technology is expected to equip citizens with the knowledge and skills on how to cope with life challenges. That is why Basic Education Programme 2013 Act, stipulates that every individual graduating from basic education shall be empowered to learn, through a programme that is rooted on sound and strong educational principles which is geared towards excellence and sound foundations for sustainable national development. Education in science and technology is an imperative tool towards sustainable scientific and technological growth without compromise on the environmental safety and well-being of the nation (Bembenutty & White, 2013). Upu and Okwara (2024) conceptualized education in science and technology as a pattern of procedures that show the relationship between functions of natural phenomena and empirical evidence in our environment. This means that education in science and technology education prepare learners to have competence and ability to interpret natural environment and coexist in fruitful harmony with local and global communities which engage in productive work that is capable of national self-sustenance. Therefore, the 9-year continuous basic education programme of the Nigerian government is expected to provide learners with this sound foundation in Basic Science and Technology so as to contribute effectively for sustainable national development.

Basic Science and Technology is a compulsory subject of 9-year basic education programme that can provide learners with adequate knowledge, skills and standards to be good citizens in search for solutions to contemporary societal problems. Basic Science and Technology as a fundamental subject is a viable tool in the critical area of science-technology fields like banking, medicine, aviation industry, and climatic-change monitoring and demographic feasibility studies (Upu & Okwara 2024).

Despite the importance of Basic Science and Technology in national development, Basic and Technology students of levels are observed to be performing poorly in the subject over the years (Benue State Examination Board, Annual Report, 2018). Adding to this report, the board further stated that this set of students find it very difficult to understand the principles,

theories and laws of science. Basic Science and Technology happens to be the fundamental subject which forms the basis of science and technology at all levels, as such this has led to the low performance of students in pure science subjects like Biology, Chemistry and Physics. The issue of low performance does not affect students only at middle and upper basic education levels but also affect their academic performance as they progress even at post-secondary school level (Janjua, Malik & Rahman 2011). In fact some of the students end up not choosing carriers of their choice, due to the poor performance in Basic Science and Technology in particular and science subjects in general. Many reasons have been put forward by different researchers on the persistent poor performance of students in Basic Science and Technology ranging from wrong perception of scientific and technological concepts by the learners to the instructional strategy employed by teachers. The question now is would homework strategy improve students' self-regulatory behavior and academic performance? This necessitated the researcher to find out whether homework strategy will enhance students' self-regulatory behavior and academic performance.

Homework strategy is one of the ways to improve students' understanding of scientific and technological knowledge and skills that lead to higher academic performance and self-regulatory behavior (Latif, & Mile 2011). This can be achieved by constant practice and hands-on activities that enhance mastery knowledge on scientific concepts. This mastery can be experienced when students are involved in doing their homework. This shows that when students are engaged in instructional homework activities, they would develop proficiency, efficiency and mastery of procedures, conceptual and content knowledge as it is applied in Basic Science and Technology which may increase performance in science and technology as they progress from one level of education to another.

Generally, homework strategy is used as an essential tool for Basic Science and Technology activities to develop mental and cognitive abilities in students (Letterman, 2013). According to Tangjinusorn and Sukavatee (2016) homework strategy provides students with opportunities to improve their learning habits, learning performance, and aims to increase their self-regulatory behavior. Homework strategy continues to be a debatable and controversial topic of discussion among scholars. Many scholars reported that homework strategy teaches students to be responsible, keeps them on check, develops time management skills, and also regulates their behavior (Tsai & Jiang 2011).

Homework as defined by Cooper (2017) is any task assigned to pupils or students by school teachers which is meant to be carried out during non-school hours. This means that homework is usually given to students to be done at home or at their own leisure time. In other words, homework can also be defined as a set of school tasks that are assigned to students by teachers to be completed outside school hours (Cooper, Robinson & Patall 2006). Instructional homework involves three important actors; students, parents, and teachers. Each of the three actors plays an important role in the effective homework completion for maximum academic performance. There is no specific time allocated for students to complete their homework, but the time of completion of any given homework depends on the child's speed and ability to regulate himself in order to ensure that the assigned homework is completed.

There are three types of homework as postulated by Ramdass and Zimmerman (2015) which are: practice, preparation, and extension homework. Practice instructional homework can be used by teachers when assigning homework tasks to promote students' engagement and meaningful learning. Practice instructional homework focuses on tasks taught in a class to increase speed, demonstrate mastery skills, review work, study for tests, and retain specific skills over time. Teachers assign practice and preparation instructional homework most often because they are more convenient and less time consuming. Practice instructional homework is more often used by teachers to increase proficiency and understanding of concepts, facts and principles (Bembenuddy & White 2013). Practice instructional homework is an essential index as far as this study is concerned, as such when a teacher uses practice instructional homework regularly in the course of teaching and learning of Basic Science and Technology it brings about a positive change in students' academic performance and self-regulatory behaviors. This is because when students are consistently practicing what they are taught at home, issue of low performance will be reduced.

Preparatory homework focuses on preparing students for the next lesson. This type of instructional homework is inherently linked to pre-learning (Nunez, *et al.*, 2011). Preparatory instructional homework is designed to encourage students to thinking about previous topic discussed in a class so as to prepare for future topics. Cooper (2008) conducted a study on 638 sixth-grade students using practice and preparation instructional homework the result reveals high impact on students' academic performance. This implies that practice and preparation instructional homework provides students with opportunity to review the material to be covered in the future lesson from the textbook and write down main ideas that help them to prepare for better learning. Preparation instructional homework help students to understand with ease that which is been taught in the classroom because they already have prior knowledge on what is been taught.

Extension homework focuses on promoting the shift of previous learning to new tasks. Extension instructional homework requires higher level or abstract thinking to occur (Prommin & Jutharat, 2019). Teachers use this type of homework to encourage students to collaborate with peers and be more creative during learning of real-life, hands-on and applicable skills

which are used to complete extension homework tasks. This provides a richer learning experience for students for better academic performance.

Academic performance simply means what someone academically achieved successfully (Upu & Okwara 2024). Factors which enhance performance include practice and coaching. These factors, if observed strictly could yield maximum and highest level of academic performance. Muijis & Reynolds (2014) observed that the teaching task is meant to impact an enduring change in the learner's academic performance and self-regulate behaviour.

Self-regulation is defined as a broad construct representative of cognitive, motivational-affective, social and physiological processes that modulate attention and emotion, in a given situation/stimulus, for the purpose of pursuing a goal (Krashen, 2005). It is supported by the interrelated cognitive skills of working memory (the ability to hold information in mind), inhibitory control (the ability to suppress a dominant response in favour of a subordinate response), and cognitive flexibility (the ability to shift attention or cognitive set) (Wyatt, & Perna, 2017). In the present study, we focus on behavioral self-regulation, which is also defined as deliberately effort to apply multiple component processes of attention or cognitive flexibility, working memory, and inhibitory control to overt, socially contextualized behaviors" and identified it as an important component for early academic performance. There is evidence that supportive school environments enhance children's development of self-regulation behaviour (Wyatt, & Perna, 2017). Furthermore, evidence suggests synergistic interactions between school environments and self-regulation skills critical to academic progress. Specifically, the impact of school environments may depend, at least partly, on early individual differences in children's self-regulation skills. For example, attending elementary schools identified as unsafe is associated with poorer self-regulation in middle childhood, but only for those children identified as having poor self-regulation skills in preschool level, (Tsai & Jiang, 2013).

The ability to regulate or manage behavior allows one to focus when there are distractions, pay attention to the most important information, take turns, wait, follow rules, adapt to new situations, do what is academically expected, suppress outbursts of anger, and take on challenges. Behavioral regulation develops gradually during childhood. This process does not happen overnight, and some children are able to cope with daily stresses more easily than others. Children's ability to manage or regulate their behavior has been identified as one of the most important prerequisites to school success (Rimm-Kaufman, Pianta, & Cox, 2010). Children must be able to sit quietly and listen to the teacher, change activities when requested to do so, and resist class distractions of touching their fellow students or taking their personal belongings which are focus distractor. The range of individual difference is the ability to self-regulation in early childhood and the job of managing a classroom of 5-year olds has been described by kindergarten teachers as akin "trying to keep crickets in a basket" (Bodrova & Leong, 2018). These individual differences in behavioral self-regulation during early childhood are predictive of academic success, with better self-regulation. Transition to formal schooling is associated with better academic performance as well as behavioral outcomes (Ramdass & Zimmerman 2015).

In this study, the researchers explore the effects of homework strategy on self-regulatory behavior and performance in basic- science and technology concepts among students in Benue state. Although schools have been identified as one of the important contexts for shaping children's behavioral development and academic performance (Slavin, 2014). Research on the relation of school context to self-regulation development is sparse. Few studies have examined classroom-level effects on self-regulation (Bodrova & Leong, 2018). Since homework is important, but most students do not take it seriously, as it helps to improve performance and self-regulatory behavior, hence this prompted the researchers to carry out this study.

Nigerian students at basic education level are seem to be performing poorly and having low self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology, because they see concepts as abstract and meaningless and which are difficult to be understood with ease (Upu & Okwara 2024). This has also created fears in the mind of students and as well dropped their performance especially at the middle basic level (Upu & Okwara 2024). For example, looking at the results from the first school leaving certificate and Basic Education Certificate Examination, we can see that pupils at these levels are performing below expectation (Benue State Examination Board, 2023). Many scholars argue that, if students will spend more time on academics' work, outside of school doing their homework it can go a long way to increase their performance and self-regulatory behavior (Slavin, 2014). In this regard the researchers have decided to examine the Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic- Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study intends to investigate Effects of Homework strategy on self-Regulatory Behavior and Performance in Basic- Science and Technology Concepts among students in Benue State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Investigate the mean rating scores in self-regulatory behavior between students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.
2. Determine the mean performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What is the difference between mean academic performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?
2. What is the difference between the mean ratings scores of self-regulatory behaviors of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?

Hypotheses

These following research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students' that were given homework after lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental, non-randomized, pre-test, post-test control group design. The sample size of 467 Middle basic II students during the 2023/2024 academic session was drawn from the population of 13,467 student using multi-stage sampling technique. Multi-stage sampling technique was used for the selection of the sampled schools. Only four schools were randomly chosen because of the experimental nature of the study. Two schools each were assigned to experimental and control group. The instruments used for data collection were Basic Science and Technology Performance Test (BSTPT) and Self-Regulatory Behaviour Inventory (SRBI), which were developed by the researchers. The validation of the instruments was done by three experts. The reliability of BSTPT and SRBI, were calculated using Cronbach Coefficient Alpha test method and Kuder-Richardson 20 formula which gave the value of 0.86 and 0.74 respectively. These values indicate that there is a positive relationship within the test items which show that items of the instruments are both internally consistent and reliable.

Basic Science and Technology teachers currently teaching in the sampled schools were used for the study in both experimental and control group as research assistants. SRBI and BSTPT were administered to students as pre-test to ascertain their initial level of performance in of BST and initial self-regulatory behaviors before treatment (teaching) commence. The control group was also taught the same contents without home at the end of each lesson. The teaching lasted for four weeks with 12 periods both in experimental and control group. Immediately after conclusion of the teaching, the SRBI and BSTPT were given as post-test and scores were recorded. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). ANCOVA was used to check the initial difference that might exist between the groups due to the random assigning of the schools.

Presentation of Results

Research Questions 1: What is the difference between the mean rating scores of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on Students' Self-regulatory Behavior Rating in BST

Instruction	N	Pre-interest		Post-interest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
With Homework	124	2.35	1.02	3.79	0.05	1.44
Without Homework	119	2.41	1.01	2.64	0.15	0.23
Total	243					
Mean difference		-0.06		1.15		1.21

(Source: field work 2024)

Result in Table 1 showed that the mean rating on students' self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology that were given homework after every lesson was higher than those taught without homework at the end of the lesson. The difference

between mean self-regulatory behavior ratings of students that were given homework and those without homework is 1.21. Hypothesis one was tested for level of significance to confirm this result in Table 2.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Mean Self-Regulatory Behavior Ratings in BST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	5067.567 ^a	2	2533.784	210.307	.000	.397
Intercept	33979.036	1	33979.036	2820.305	.000	.415
Pre-test	209.274	1	209.274	17.370	.002	.024
Self-regulatory behavior	413.408	1	413.408	12.814	.000	.76
Error	7710.694	239	32.262			
Total	1081300.000	243				
Corrected Total	12778.261	242				

a. R Squared = .397 (Adjusted R Squared = .393)

(Source: field work 2024)

Findings in Table 2 indicated that F-value for self-regulatory behavior was 12.814 at the significance value of 0.000, which is less than the p-value of 0.05. Based on this findings hypothesis two which stated that there is no significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework is rejected. This means that there is significant difference between the mean rating of self-regulatory behavior of students that were given homework and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework. To assess effect size between the groups the computed value of partial eta squared gave the value of 0.76. This value indicates that there is high effect size between the groups that was given homework after every lesson and taught were BST without homework

Research Questions 2: What is the mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without homework?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' performance Scores in BST

Group	N	Pre- BSTAT		Post- BSTAT		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Experimental	124	34.74	1.02	66.42	0.93	31.68
Control	119	34.63	1.03	54.62	1.06	19.99
Total	243					
Mean difference			0.11		11.80	11.69

(Source: field work 2024)

The result in Table 1 shows that students that were given homework after every lesson have higher mean scores than students that were not given any homework. The mean difference between experimental and control group was 11.69. This shows that students that were given homework after every lesson of Basic Science and Technology have achieved higher than those that were not given any homework. This result was further investigated by testing of hypothesis 1 as shown in Table 4.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on Students' Achievement in BST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Eta Squared
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corrected Model	9893.146 ^a	2	4946.673	328.617	.000	.340
Intercept	19239.312	1	19239.312	1,278.105	.000	.110
Pretest	28.652	1	28.652	1.903	.122	.041
Group	687.486	1	687.486	45.671	.003	.76
Error	3597.763	239	15.053			
Total	405400.000	243				
Corrected Total	4490.909	242				

a. R Squared = .199 (Adjusted R Squared = .190)

(Source: field work 2024)

Findings in Table 4 revealed that the experimental group had F-value of 45.671 at the significance value of 0.003, this significance value is less than p-value of 0.05 (i.e. $p = 0.05 > 0.003$). With this result, null hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework is rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference between mean academic performance scores of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught Basic Science and Technology without any homework. The partial eta squared was investigated which gave a value of 0.76. This value indicates that there is a high effect size between the experimental and control group.

Summary of Major Findings

1. There is no significant difference between mean academic performances of students that were given homework after every lesson and those that were taught BST without homework.
2. There is no significant difference between mean ratings of self-regulatory behaviour of students that were given homework after every lesson and those were taught BST without any homework.

Discussion of findings

Before the commencement of the treatment in this study pretest was used to assess equivalent knowledge of students' academic performance and self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology. This means that any observed differences in the results are due to the treatment. The results of the analysis of data on research questions and null hypotheses are hereby discussed.

The results of the finding of this study showed that there is a significant difference in mean self-regulatory behavior of students in Basic Science and Technology. This indicates that homework strategy improved self-regulatory behavior of students in schools. The findings of this study agreed with Bembenutty and White (2013) and Cooper (2017) who found that regular use of homework strategy during teaching served as a tool for checking and regulating students' behavior at home and in the school.

The results of the findings of this study in respect to academic performance of students that were given homework and those that were taught without homework showed a significant difference in their mean scores. This implies that instructional homework had improved the academic performance of students in Basic Science and Technology. This finding was supported that of Paudel (2012) and Tsai and Jiag (2013) who reported a significant difference in the mean academic performance of students that were exposed to instructional homework in schools. The author concluded that the difference often observed by researchers in students' academic performance cannot be attributes only to their knowledge, but also to the nature of instructions (teaching approach) the students were exposed to.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings the researchers concluded that homework strategy enhances both academic performance of students and self-regulatory behavior in Basic Science and Technology.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made that: Teachers should use homework strategy regularly when teaching Basic Science and Technology at all levels of basic education. Parents and guardian should encourage and direct their children in the appropriate way of do homework. Stakeholders in education should organize seminars and conferences to train serving BST teachers on how to use appropriate homework strategy to enhance students' academic performance and improve their self-regulatory behaviour.

Acknowledgements

We the researchers wish to express our appreciations to all the authors whose works are used in this work. We are also very grateful to the principals who permitted the use of their schools and resources, including students and Basic Science and Technology teachers for this study. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the research assistants employed in the course of this study, and the validators of the instruments for their inputs. We also wish to acknowledge the editors and the editorial board of Zamfara International Journal of Education for vetting and improving the quality of this work.

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